

AN ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE REVIEWS OF STUDIES CONDUCTED IN INDIA AND ABROAD REGARDING THE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, STUDY HABIT AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF THE STUDENTS OF DIFFERENT LEVELS.

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ABSTRACT:

Literature review is a very important aspect of research as it helps us to analyze the problem in hand and give us a rough idea of the probable results. This study aims at understanding the variables emotional intelligence, study-habit and socio-economic status and how they affect the academic achievement of the students worldwide. The researcher has tried to include studies in the nation as well as abroad to understand the traits of the students all over the world. The values of Pearson's coefficient of correlation in each case has been taken into account and the researcher has tried to find out the percentages of positive, negative or no correlation with the above mentioned variables and academic achievement. It has been observed that emotional intelligence has a cent percent positive correlation with academic achievement, while study habits and socio-economic status reports negative and no correlation along with positive correlation with academic achievement. It can be said without a doubt that these three variables are definite effectors of academic achievement.

KEYWORDS:

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, STUDY HABIT, SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS, ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

2nd November 2024

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

4th November 2024

1. INTRODUCTION

Education and academic achievement are two sides of the same coin that can't be separated. The factors on which academic achievement depend on are layered and complex. Even then the researcher has decided to filter out three variables on which academic achievement depends. They are namely emotional intelligence, study habit and socio-economic status. A detailed study of various researches has led the researcher to the idea of comparing various foreign and Indian researches that have worked on the same variables in the hope of finding a link between the type of dependence that the academic achievement Indian students and foreign students exhibit on these variables.

2. DEFINITION OF IMPORTANT KEY WORDS

- Emotional intelligence – EI refers to the ability of an individual to control and evaluate emotions. It can mean being aware of one's and others feelings. In the words of Travis Bradberry and Jean Greaves (2009), "Emotional Intelligence is the 'something' in each of us that is a bit intangible. It affects how we manage behaviour, navigate social complexities, and make personal decisions that achieve positive results."
- Study habit – SH means habits that a person follows daily for effective study. It refers to

organizing learning and reading regularly to cope up with new knowledge. It can also be considered synonymous to practice. In the words of Malcom Gladwell (2008), "Practice isn't the thing you do once you're good. It's the thing that makes you good."

- Socio-economic status- SES refers to the quantity and quality of material goods and services available to a given population. It depends on education, income and economic opportunity of an individual. In the words of Illeana ROS-Lehtinen, "No matter where you are from, no matter what your socio-economic status is, every person can achieve his or her dreams."
- Academic achievement – Academic achievement is the extent to which a student has their short-term or short-term education goals. It is commonly measured through examinations or continuous assessments.

3. A brief discussion on related Indian researches on emotional intelligence and academic achievement:

The brief report on the relation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of some selected Indian researches are summarized in the table 1 below-

TABLE1: TABLE SUMMARIZING FINDINGS OF INDIAN RESEARCHES ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE (EI) AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT (AA)

SL.NO	Area	Author and year	Findings
1	Delhi	M.K.Sharma (2011)	AA has positive significant relationship with EI (r = 0.2633)
2	Kanyakumari	A.S.Arul Lawrence, T.Deepa (2013)	No significant relationship between EI &AA (r = 0.165)
3	Tamil Nadu	D.Thomas Alexander (2017)	EI has a positive relation (Not significant) with scholastic performance (r = 0.104)
4	Banaras	Priyanka Rowniyar (2020)	AA was found to vary significantly with EI (r = 0.534)
5	Odisha	Dr.Lopamudra Dash,Chinmay Bairiganjan(2021)	A positive correlation was found between EI & AA (r= 0.306)

Summarizing the findings of Indian researches, we can see that a time span of ten years have been covered. All the researches have been conducted on school students of varying ages. As can be seen from the table 1 above, all the chosen researches show that academic achievement has a positive relation with emotional intelligence with varying values of correlation as shown. The values may not be

significant in each case but that depends on various other external factors also. What can be concluded from this table is that, academic achievement of school students has a positive relation with emotional intelligence.

4. A brief discussion on related foreign researches on emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

TABLE 2: TABLE SUMMARIZING FINDINGS OF FOREIGN RESEARCHES ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT.

SL.NO	Area	Author and year	Findings
1	West Indies	Grace.A.Fayambo	Emotional intelligence factors are positively related to academic achievement as- i. Attending emotions (r = 0.58,P<0.05) Positive expressivity (r = 0.44, P<0.05) Empathetic concern (r = 0.36, P<0.05) Responsive joy (r = 0.33, P<0.05) Emotion based decision making (r = 0.33, P<0.05) Responsible distress (r = 0.18, P<0.05) and the factor negative expressivity is negatively correlated to academic achievement (r = -0.50, P<0.05)
2	Bangladesh Gopalganj	Nusrat sharmin, Masuma Parvin, Nasrin Nahar (December 2019)	Academic achievement is found to be positively correlated with emotional intelligence (P<0.05)

3	Malaysia shah Alam Selango	Maizatul Akmal, Md. Rohzan,Norhas Linda Hassan, Norhafizah Aled, Halil (2012)	There is a positive and weak relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement (r = 0.084, P=0.193)
4	China Yiwu district	Abdo Hasan Al-Qadri, Wei Zhao. (2021)	The five factors of emotional intelligence are positively correlated with academic achievement - Intrapersonal skills (r = 0.35) Intrapersonal skills (r = 0.50) Stress management (r = 0.49) iv. Adaptability (r = 0.56) v. General mood (r = 0.64)
5	Spain	Ana Maria Martinez Rartinezet al. (2022)	Emotional intelligence positively predicted academic achievement ($\beta = 0.001$)

As we can see from the data accommodated in table 2, emotional intelligence is positively correlated to academic achievement. The first three studies are done on under graduate students while the bottom two are conducted on school students. The data is again taken from different countries as mentioned. The data is again taken from

different countries as mentioned. So we can conclude that, emotional intelligence is a positive predictor of academic achievement irrespective of country or age of students.

5. A brief discussion on related indian researches on study habit and academic achievement.

TABLE 3- TABLE SUMMARIZING FINDINGS OF INDIAN RESEARCHES ON STUDY HABIT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT.

SL.NO	Area	Author and year	Findings
1	Pune	Evans Atsiaya Siah, Julius K.Maiyo (2015)	A positive and significant correlation is found between study habit and academic achievement. (r = 0.66)
2	Delhi	Sheetal Kapur (2018)	A positive correlation is seen between learning strategies and scholastic achievement (r = 0.266)
3	Ludhiana Punjab	Reeta Arora (2016)	A r value of 0.735 shores a high positive correlation between study habit and academic achievement.
4	Meghalaya	Welbirth stone L Nonglait, Garelt B.Lailthma (2020)	The r value was found to be -0.283 which shoues that study habit and academic achievement are negatively correlated.

5	Dibrugarh	Dr. Rajinder Singh, Jharna Gohain (2022)	A weak and positive correlation (r = 0.03) Is found between study habit and academic achievement.
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Summarizing the findings of the papers reviewed we can see that the range of the r-value denoting the correlation between study habit and academic achievement varies from negative to low positive to high positive. This shows that study habit may not be a very concrete sole

decider for high academic achievement. There are definitely other factors that assist study habit in causing a variation in academic achievement.

6. A brief discussion on related foreign researches on study habit and academic achievement.

TABLE 4: TABLE SUMMARIZING FINDINGS OF FOREIGN RESEARCHES ON STUDY HABIT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT.

SL.NO	Area	Author and year	Findings
1	Kermanshah	Haleh Jafari, Abbas Aghali, Alireza Khatony (2019)	A positive and significant relationship was found between academic achievement and study habit (r =0.235)
2	Kaski	Tek Narayan Poudel (2016)	Study habit was found to be a significant predictor of position of students in class.
3	Munich	Toheeb Olatunji (2021)	There is a significant relation between study habit and academic achievement.
4	Nigeria	Abdulkareem Munir (2022)	The correlation between study habit and academic achievement is r = 0.045 which is weak positive but not significant
5	United Kingdoms	Shabir Ahmed Rana, Rukhsana Kausar (2011)	No significant relation between study habit and academic achievement is noted.

As seen for Indian studies, we see that the correlation between study habit and academic achievement is variable. It varies from very low positive insignificant to

significant. So we can conclude that academic achievement is not always predicted correctly by study habit.

7. A brief discussion on related indian researches on socio- economic state and academic achievement

TABLE 5: TABLE SUMMARIZING FINDINGS OF INDIAN RESEARCHES ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATE AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT.

SL.NO	Area	Author and year	Findings
1	Meghalaya	Toba Lamara (2022)	There is no significant relation between socio- economic states and academic achievement
2	Allahabad	Pandey Rama shanker (2019)	The correlation between socio-economic states and academic achievement is 0.6379 ❖ For boys, the correlation is 0.6266 & for girls, it is 0.6609

❖ 3	❖ Murshidabad W.B.	Md.Rofikul Iseam, Zebun Nisa Khan (2017)	❖ Correlation between socio-economic states and academic achievement is 0.347. A significant difference is noted between the academic achievement of high and low socio- economic states (t-value of 14.830)
4	Jammu & Kashmir Anantnag Dist	Sheeraz Ahmad Rather (2013)	A significant difference is between academic achievement scores of lower and higher socio-economic states. Higher socio-economic states students having higher academic achievement than lower ones.
5	Hyderabad	P.swarnalata (2021)	There is a significant different between academic achievement high, medium and low socio-economic states groups. ❖ The correlation of academic achievement between low and high socio- economic states is 0.225 for s.sc, 0.385 for S.C, 0.479 for Maths and 0.329 for language.

As seen in the Table 5, we can see in all the four researches, the SES plays an important role in the academic achievement. Only in the first tabulated research in table 5, SES done not correlate significantly with academic achievement. So, we can conclude that SES is an

important effector of academic achievement except may be for some special areas.

8. A brief discussion on related foreign researches on socio- economic states and academic achievement

TABLE 6: TABLE SUMMARIZING FINDINGS OF FOREIGN RESEARCHES ON STUDY HABIT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT.

SL.NO	Area	Author and year	Findings
1	Lanzou	Shifeng Li, Qiongying,Xu, Ruixue Xa (2019)	❖ Achiment in Chinese was significantly predicted by SES. ($\beta = 0.23$) Achievement in Mathematics was significantly predicted by SES ($\beta = 0.20$).
2	Seattle	Lucy, A. durie, Mc. Katie AMc Laughlin, (et.al) (2021)	Academic achievement in children were positively associated with home assessment ($\beta = 0.478$), care giver education ($\beta = 0.547$) & income to needs ($\beta = 0.222$).
3	Turkey	Ozgen Ersan, Michael C Rodriguez (2020)	The correlation between Mathematics achievement and SES was 0.52 at student level, 0.80 at school level.

4	Ethiopia	Gemechu Abera Gobena (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Parent’s education had a statistically strong relationship ($r = 0.73$) to academic achievement Family education contributed 40.96% to the academic achievement of students.
5	USA	Jennifer Barry (2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ As the SES of the students rises, the test scores rise by 0.118 points. ❖ Family factors (income & education) cause greatest variance of test scores about 62%.

As seen in the above table 6, we can see that all the researches show a positive correlation between socio economic status and academic achievement. So we can see that even if there is a division of countries and ages of the students, socio-economic status serves as a strong predictor for academic achievement of the students.

9. Comparison of Indian and foreign researches

Percentage of positive correlations of the variable’s emotional intelligence, study habit and socio-economic status with academic achievement are shown in the table below.

TABLE 7: PERCENTAGE OF POSITIVE CORRELATIONS OF INDIAN AND FOREIGN RESEARCHES

Origin of research	Emotional Intelligence	Study Habit	Socio Economic Status
Indian	100%	80%	80%
Foreign	100%	80%	100%

FIG1: COMPARISON OF POSITIVE CORRELATIONS IN FOREIGN AND INDIAN RESEARCHES

TABLE 8: PERCENTAGE OF NEGATIVE AND NOT SIGNIFICANT CORRELATIONS OF THE VARIABLE’S EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, STUDY HABIT AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS WITH ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Origin of research	Emotional Intelligence	Study Habit	Socio Economic Status
Indian	0	20%(negative)	20% (not significant)
Foreign	0	20% (not significant)	0

FIG 2: PERCENTAGE OF NEGATIVE AND NOT SIGNIFICANT CORRELATIONS

10. CONCLUSION:

Combining the results obtained from all the researches from India and abroad we can say that, the three variables chosen, namely, emotional intelligence, study habit and socio-economic status are quite strong predictors of academic achievement. The sheer variety of area, level of students and diversity of background guarantees an impartial or unbiased judgment. Care should be taken to develop the emotional intelligence of students from a very tender age. The curriculum should include ways to develop study habit and guide students to practice such good habits. As the socio-economic status of a family is not

under control completely, the government should cater to the needs of the students by providing scholarships and the schools should motivate and guide the students towards utilizing the benefits of these scholarships. A united effort from all the stakeholders of education can ensure the world a brighter future.

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